

Beneficial Usage of Instruments in Teaching Music

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Abstract. This study examined the extent of availability of musical resources and their influence on music education outcomes in selected public schools within the Mati Northwest District, Mati North West District, and Mati City Schools Division. Guided by a descriptive-correlational research design, the study surveyed 122 participants to assess five domains of musical resource availability quantity and variety of instruments, technology and audiovisual equipment, music software and applications, music libraries and sheet music, and rehearsal spaces and four domains of music education outcomes musical proficiency, performance quality, creativity and expression, and ensemble participation. Results showed that the availability of musical resources was generally extensive, while music education outcomes were moderately extensive. However, correlation analysis indicated no significant relationship between resource availability and education outcomes ($r = 0.065$, $p = 0.477$). Regression analysis revealed that only the availability of rehearsal spaces significantly influenced music education outcomes ($\beta = 0.439$, $p = 0.008$). These findings underscore the importance of aligning resource utilization with instructional strategies and emphasize the value of rehearsal environments in enhancing student learning experiences in music. The study recommends targeted investment in rehearsal spaces and enhanced teacher training on integrating music resources into pedagogical practice.

KEY WORDS

1. music education 2. musical resources 3. rehearsal spaces

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1. Introduction

Resource constraints on music education in elementary schools highlight challenges that impact musical education worldwide. Economic disparities mean that schools in financially disadvantaged areas often require more resources, resulting in unequal opportunities for students to access instruments, technology, and qualified instructors. The allocation of resources varies across educational systems, with some schools allocating limited budgets to music programs due to competing priorities. The lack of funding and resources for music programs, as well as the digital divide, are two global challenges that need to be addressed. To ensure access to a comprehensive and enriching music education for all elementary school students, we must advocate for equitable resource distribution, promote and use technology (Coppola, 2021). Additionally, Draper (2023) suggests that fostering partnerships with private organizations, philanthropic foundations, and community stakeholders can provide supplementary resources, tools, and technology to schools in need. Integrating music education into broader policies and emphasizing its intrinsic value in holistic student development can help secure

sustained support. Leveraging technology, especially in the digital age, is crucial for overcoming resource limitations. Online platforms and educational apps can supplement traditional teaching methods, offering interactive and accessible tools for music instruction. The selection of musical repertoire is crucial. However, is equally evident. Therefore, it is crucial to explicitly acknowledge (González Ben, 2023). School libraries help students develop reading habits and a reading culture, but their capacity for music appreciation and literature often needs improvement. A study by Dilekçi (2022) found that two-thirds of schools had libraries, but these libraries mostly contained classical works, with limited digitalization and a range of genres. Physical conditions must be improved, and the variety and quality of documents increased, to enhance the effective use of libraries. In the context of Philippine education, various approaches exist to address concerns related to resource constraints in music education in elementary schools (Cul et al., 2023). Firstly, strategic policy reforms are necessary to ensure a fair distribution of resources, with a particular focus on allocating adequate funds for music programs in economically disadvantaged areas. This requires a joint effort between government agencies, educational institutions, and advocacy groups to prioritize the significance of music education and secure the necessary financial support. Forming partnerships with local musicians or community organizations can offer valuable expertise and resources, which are essential for effective music education that fosters creativity. Inclusive teaching practices ensure that all students participate actively. Teachers can secure additional support through grants and fundraising. Integrating music with other subjects optimizes resources and enhances learning. It addresses challenges and offers well-rounded musical instruction (Ben, 2022). Juan et al. (2023) shared the educational status of the people in the Visayas Region. The study

found that art is being modernized and incorporated into a form that the general public appreciates. The author recommends innovating and exploring ways to form an ensemble using ethnic instruments, holding various art festivals, and engaging in cultural exchanges. In the locality of Mati City, the availability of musical resources in schools is still challenging, which encapsulates the extent to which a learning institution is equipped to provide students with a rich and comprehensive music education experience. It encompasses a diverse range of elements, including the accessibility of musical instruments, technology, sheet music, rehearsal spaces, and other materials that are fundamental to the teaching and learning of music. Thus, this study is presented.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is grounded in the theory of socioeconomic factors, which explores the impact of these factors on educational outcomes. Music education can be applied to understand how resource constraints, often linked to economic factors, influence the quality and accessibility of music education in elementary schools. This framework can delve into the disparities in resource distribution, access to private music lessons, and the musical opportunities available to students from different socioeconomic backgrounds. Burak (2020) said that the socioeconomic theory provides a comprehensive lens through which to analyze and understand the implications of resource constraints on music education in elementary schools. In the study context, this theoretical framework can be applied to investigate the direct correlation between economic factors and the availability of musical resources. Aydin, Elif; Gül, Gülnihal (2022) stated that it examines how varying levels of economic resources among schools contribute to disparities in access to musical instruments, technology, and qualified instructors. This framework helps uncover potential socioeconomic barriers students may face

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

in pursuing music education, examining how limited resources may disproportionately affect schools in economically disadvantaged areas. By applying socioeconomic theory, the study aims to illuminate the systemic challenges arising from economic disparities and their manifestations in music education.

The microsystem, which encompasses individual students and teachers, is scrutinized

to understand how resource constraints directly affect the day-to-day experiences of those involved in music education. The mesosystem analysis examines the interactions among students, teachers, and parents, providing insights into how collaboration and communication influence the effectiveness of music education programs.

2. Methodology

This chapter delineates the study’s processes and procedures, encompassing the selection of the research design, identification of respondents and the employed sampling method, determination of research instruments for data collection, outlining the procedural steps, ethical considerations, and culminating in the data analysis. These sequential steps are deemed indispensable, ensuring the appropriateness and accuracy of the data collection, analysis, and interpretation processes to yield robust and reliable results.

2.1. Research Design—The study adopted a descriptive-correlational research design, following the non-experimental approach outlined by Creswell (2020). This design was

selected to explore relationships between two or more variables without intervening or manipulating them. Instead, it centers on observing and analyzing existing associations between

these variables. Furthermore, the descriptive-correlational research design is employed to elucidate and clarify the relationships between variables. Its primary objective is to unveil connections between variables and offer insights that can be leveraged to predict future events. Typically applied in exploratory studies or when researchers aim to establish relationships between variables, this design proves valuable for its capacity to illuminate associations among variables without resorting to experimental manipulation. In the study "Beneficial Usage of Instruments in Teaching Music in Mati northwest district," used a descriptive-correlational research design, characterized as a non-experimental approach according to Creswell (2014), serves as the methodological framework. This design is aptly applied to examine the relationships between various variables associated with resource constraints in the context of music education. Rather than intervening or manipulating the variables, the study aims to observe and analyze the existing associations between limited resources and their impact on music education. Through the use of surveys, interviews, or other data collection methods, the researchers seek to elucidate and clarify the intricate connections between the quantity and variety of musical instruments, technology, budgets, and other resources in elementary schools. By adopting the descriptive-correlational design, the study endeavors to provide a comprehensive understanding of how resource constraints might influence the quality of music education in elementary schools, offering valuable insights that can inform future educational policies and practices. This approach proves particularly beneficial for its ability to uncover associations and patterns among variables without resorting to experimental manipulation, making it well-suited for exploring complex and real-world phenomena such as resource constraints in music education.

2.2. *Ethical Consideration*—The ethical considerations of this study will focus on safe-

guarding the rights, privacy, and well-being of the teacher-respondents. This will involve strict adherence to ethical principles, including maintaining confidentiality, obtaining informed consent, and ensuring voluntary participation. Confidentiality measures will be implemented to protect respondents' identities and responses, preventing any potential risks associated with disclosure. Informed consent will be secured by providing clear information about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential implications, allowing participants to make an informed decision about their involvement.

Social Value

As a researcher, I recognize teachers' crucial role in shaping the quality of education, and this study holds significant social value in addressing their professional needs. Understanding the challenges teachers face handling multiple subjects, I aim to contribute to policies and programs that enhance their instructional effectiveness and overall well-being. This research will provide insights into how professional development and resource support can be improved, ultimately benefiting both educators and their students. I hope to impact the education system meaningfully, ensuring that teaching and learning conditions are improved for a more equitable and effective learning environment.

Informed Consent and Assent

I understand the importance of ensuring that teacher-respondents are fully aware of their rights and the purpose of this study before participating. I will obtain informed consent by clearly explaining the study's objectives, procedures, potential benefits, and any possible risks. Respondents will be given the opportunity to ask questions and will only participate voluntarily after fully understanding the research process. Their right to withdraw at any time without consequences will be emphasized, ensuring that their participation is based on free will and trust. Although informed consent is the primary

ethical requirement for teacher-respondents in this study, I also recognize the importance of assent in cases requiring additional permissions or approvals. If participants need institutional clearance or administrative approval, I will ensure that they fully understand the study before agreeing to participate. Assent ensures that all stakeholders involved in the research process acknowledge and respect the voluntary nature of participation.

Vulnerability of Research Respondents

As a researcher, I acknowledge that teacher-respondents may face certain vulnerabilities that must be carefully considered throughout this study. Teachers handling multiple subjects often experience heavy workloads, limited resources, and institutional pressures, which may affect their willingness to share honest insights. To protect them, I will ensure that their participation remains confidential and that their responses are anonymized to prevent any potential repercussions. I will create a safe and supportive environment where they feel comfortable discussing their experiences without fear of judgment or negative consequences. I am committed to conducting ethical research that values their perspectives while safeguarding their rights and well-being.

Privacy and Confidentiality

I recognize the importance of protecting the privacy and confidentiality of teacher-respondents throughout this study. I will ensure that all personal information and responses remain anonymous and securely stored, preventing unauthorized access or disclosure. Data will be reported in a way that does not reveal individual identities or specific schools, ensuring that participants feel safe in sharing their honest insights. Strict ethical guidelines will be followed to handle sensitive information responsibly. I aim to foster a research environment built on trust, where respondents can participate without fear of personal or professional risks.

Risk, Benefits and Safety

As a researcher, I am committed to minimizing any potential risks while maximizing the benefits for teacher-respondents in this study. The risks involved are minimal but may include discomfort in discussing professional challenges or concerns about confidentiality. To address this, I will ensure that participation remains voluntary, responses are anonymized, and a respectful environment is maintained throughout the research process. On the other hand, this study offers significant benefits, such as identifying gaps in professional development, advocating for better instructional support, and contributing to policies that enhance teachers' working conditions. I will also prioritize the safety and well-being of respondents by adhering to ethical research practices, ensuring that their participation leads to meaningful improvements without any harm or undue stress.

Justice

As a researcher, I am committed to ensuring fairness and equity in this study by upholding the principle of justice for all teacher-respondents. I will ensure that participation is inclusive, providing equal opportunities for teachers from different schools, backgrounds, and levels of experience to share their insights. No respondent will be excluded based on factors such as location, tenure, or access to professional development. Additionally, the study's findings will be used to benefit all teachers, not just a select group, by contributing to policies and programs that enhance instructional support.

Transparency

As a researcher, I am committed to maintaining transparency throughout the entire research process to ensure that teacher-respondents fully understand their participation and the study's purpose. I will provide clear and honest information about the research objectives, methodology, and how the collected data will be used. Respondents will be informed of their rights, including participation's voluntary nature and

ability to withdraw at any time without consequences. Any potential limitations or biases in the study will also be disclosed to maintain the integrity of the research. I aim to build trust with participants and ensure that the study remains ethical, credible, and beneficial to the teaching community.

Qualification of the Researcher

I recognize the responsibility of conducting this study with professionalism, expertise, and ethical integrity. My background in educational research, curriculum development, and technical assistance equips me with the necessary skills to design and implement a methodologically sound study.

I have experience in data collection, analysis, and ethical research practices, ensuring that the study is conducted rigorously and fairly. I am committed to continuous learning and adherence to ethical research standards to safeguard the rights and well-being of teacher-respondents.

Conflict of Interest

As a researcher, I am committed to maintaining objectivity and integrity throughout this study by ensuring that no personal, professional, or institutional affiliations influence the research process. I will take necessary precautions to prevent any biases in data collection, analysis, and interpretation, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences of teacher-respondents. If any potential conflicts of interest arise, such as affiliations with educational institutions or prior relationships with participants, I will disclose them transparently and take appropriate measures to minimize their impact. My primary goal is to conduct this study fairly and ethically, ensuring that the results contribute meaningfully to improving teacher support and professional development without any undue external influence.

Adequacy of Facilities

As a researcher, I recognize the importance of having adequate facilities to ensure

the smooth and efficient conduct of this study. I will utilize appropriate venues, technology, and research tools necessary for data collection, including spaces conducive to Key Informant Interviews (KII) and Focus Group Discussions (FGD). Digital resources, such as secure data storage and transcription software, will also be used to maintain accuracy and confidentiality in handling research findings. Additionally, I will ensure that all materials needed for the study, such as questionnaires, recording devices, and documentation tools, are readily available and properly managed. I aim to conduct a well-organized and ethical research process that upholds the credibility and reliability of the study.

Community Involvement

As a researcher, I recognize the significance of community involvement in ensuring the relevance and impact of this study. Engaging teachers, school administrators, and other stakeholders will provide valuable insights into the challenges and needs of educators handling multiple subjects. I will actively seek input from the teaching community through discussions, consultations, and collaborative exchanges to ensure that the study reflects their real experiences. I will share findings with relevant stakeholders to encourage collective action and policy recommendations that benefit both teachers and students. I aim to create a research study that is not only data-driven but also grounded in practical solutions that contribute to long-term improvements in the education system.

2.3. *Research Respondents*—The study's participants were elementary school teachers from the Mati North West District in Mati City. To determine the appropriate sample size, the researcher applied Slovin's formula, ensuring a representative selection from a total population of 170 teachers. Based on this calculation, a specific number of respondents was identified and randomly selected from various schools within the district. This sampling approach ensures that the collected data accurately reflects the per-

spectives and experiences of teachers handling multiple subjects, providing valuable insights into their professional development needs and instructional challenges. After the random selection, the chosen respondents were notified through online platforms and face-to-face communication, taking into account the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they were briefed on the study's purpose, significance, and how it contributes to their professional development. One of the key qualifications for respondents in this study is that they must be currently employed as elementary school teachers within the Mati North West District. This ensures that participants have direct experience with the instructional challenges and responsibilities associated with teaching in this specific educational context. Their active engagement in the district's teaching environment allows them to provide firsthand insights into the realities of curriculum implementation, instructional strategies, and professional development opportunities available in their schools. Another important criterion for inclusion is that the respondents must be handling multiple subjects within their assigned grade levels. This requirement ensures that the study gathers data from teachers who are directly experiencing the complexities of managing different subject areas, adapting various curricula, and balancing instructional strategies. By selecting multi-subject teachers, the study can effectively explore the impact of workload distribution, resource availability, and professional support on teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Additionally, participants must have a minimum of three years of teaching experience. This criterion ensures that the respondents have accumulated sufficient professional experience to provide meaningful reflections on their instructional practices, chal-

lenges, and the effectiveness of training programs they have attended. Teachers with at least three years in the profession will likely encounter various pedagogical difficulties and can offer valuable recommendations for improving teacher support systems within the district.

2.4. Research Instrument—A dedicated endeavor was undertaken to gather and analyze literature, extracting concepts that shaped the content and provided backing for the instrument and its associated components. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature, as the authors argued. The survey questionnaire had two parts, one of which determined the extent of the availability of musical resources in school in terms of the quantity and variety of instruments, technology and audiovisual equipment, music software and educational apps, music libraries, and sheet music and rehearsal spaces. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of music education outcomes in terms of student musical proficiency, performance quality, creativity and expression, and ensemble participation. Furthermore, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest analysis to assess validity and reliability, using Cronbach's Alpha at a 0.05 level of confidence. This analysis yielded an alpha Cronbach's coefficient of 0.960, indicating a 96.0% level of confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2020). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of the availability of musical resources in school in terms of quantity of variety of instruments, technology and audiovisual equipment, music software and educational apps, music libraries and sheet music and rehearsal spaces. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—In order to gather data for a research project, various

important steps must be taken, including obtaining permission to conduct the study in an ethi-

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation on the Availability of Musical Resources in School

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The availability of musical resources in school is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The availability of musical resources in school is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The availability of musical resources in school is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The availability of musical resources in school is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The availability of musical resources in school is not manifested

cal manner. This is crucial for upholding basic principles such as transparency, respect, and responsible research practices. The procedures for this process follow the policies of Rizal Memorial Colleges. As part of the formal request, researchers outline their intentions regarding data collection, analysis, and dissemination, aligning them with the overall research objectives. Any concerns or questions that recipients may have been addressed proactively in this communication, providing reassurance about ethical safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the potential benefits of the study. The formal request for permission explicitly seeks authorization to proceed, emphasizing the critical role of their support in ensuring the research’s success. Permission to conduct the study. In May 2024, prior to data collection, the researcher obtained necessary permissions from the relevant authorities, including the research adviser, the Dean of Rizal Memorial Colleges, and the

top management of DepEd Mati City Division through the appropriate channels. This involved submitting a comprehensive research proposal outlining study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided detailed information about the study’s purpose, goals, and methods for data collection, analysis, and reporting. Furthermore, in June 2024, the researcher took steps to ensure that all participants were fully informed about the study, their rights, and the nature of their involvement. Informed consent was obtained from each participant before their participation in the study. For distributing and retrieving questionnaires during the last week of June 2024, the researcher maintained a commitment to data accuracy and completeness. These processes were conducted with a standardized and systematic approach, ensuring reliability in the collection of responses from participants.

2.6. Data Analysis—Mean scores and standard deviation

Were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of the availabil-

ity of musical resources in school, and statement number two (2) on the extent of music education outcomes in Mati North West District, Mati City Schools Division.

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation on Music Education Outcomes

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The music education outcomes is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The music education outcomes is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The music education outcomes is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The music education outcomes is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The music education outcomes is not manifested

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r Was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between the availability of musical resources in school and music education outcomes. Simple Linear Regression analysis Was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of the availability of musical resources

in school that significantly influence music education outcomes (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey’s Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results were yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data collected in relation to the study’s stated problems. The results are organized according to the specific sub-problems, beginning with the extent of musical resources available in schools, followed by the outcomes of music education among learners. The chapter further examines the relationship between the availability of musical resources and educational outcomes and identifies which specific domains of resource availability significantly influence music learning.

3.1. The Extent of Availability of Musical Resources in Schools—The availability of musical resources in schools refers to the accessibility and adequacy of tools, materials, and spaces that support the effective teaching and learning of music. These resources encompass a wide array of elements, including the quantity and variety of instruments, technology and audiovisual equipment, music software and educational applications, music libraries and sheet music,

and rehearsal spaces. Their presence, quality, and usability are fundamental in shaping students’ musical experiences, instructional delivery, and overall outcomes in music education. According to Abril and Gault (2021), the richness of a school’s music program is often contingent upon the availability of essential resources. Schools that invest in diverse and functional musical instruments—ranging from traditional to contemporary—enable learners to explore a

wider range of musical styles, techniques, and ensemble formats. Furthermore, the integration of technology and audiovisual tools, such as smartboards, projectors, and sound systems, enhances music instruction by facilitating audiovisual demonstrations and playback opportunities that strengthen students' auditory discrimination and musical comprehension. Music software and educational applications, including notation tools, composition programs, and digital audio workstations, further extend learning by fostering creativity and individualized learning pathways. As highlighted by Ruthmann and Mantie (2022), digital tools promote self-directed learning and musical creativity, especially when traditional resources are limited. In addition, music libraries and sheet music collections remain vital in supporting theoretical instruction, sight-reading, and repertoire expansion. Access to a range of printed and digital scores ensures that students encounter both historical and contemporary works, which are crucial to developing well-rounded musical literacy. Lastly, rehearsal spaces, such as soundproof rooms or designated music halls, are indispensable for practical sessions and ensemble training. The physical environment must be conducive to focused learning, acoustic accuracy, and safe instrument handling. As posited by Hammel and Hourigan (2023), spatial limitations can severely restrict group practice and performance opportunities, particularly

These findings are consistent with recent research that emphasizes the importance of comprehensive resource availability in promoting high-quality music education. For instance, Abril and Gault (2021) emphasized that effective music instruction is closely tied to the presence of diverse and modern instructional materials, including digital tools and culturally inclusive content. Moreover, Park and Bauer (2022) found that students' musical creativity

in schools located in under-resourced or rural areas. In summary, the availability of musical resources has a significant impact on both pedagogical practices and students' musical development. A well-equipped school environment supports not only skill acquisition and artistic expression but also equitable access to quality music education. Table 1 summarizes the overall availability of musical resources in schools, based on five key domains: quantity and variety of instruments, technology and audiovisual equipment, music software and educational applications, music libraries and sheet music, and rehearsal spaces. The composite mean score is 3.487, interpreted as Extensive, which indicates that schools across the Mati Northwest District, Mati North West District, and Mati City Schools Division demonstrate a high level of resource provision in support of music education. Among the five domains, technology and audiovisual equipment received the highest rating ($M = 3.74$), underscoring the schools' substantial investment in digital infrastructure that enhances teaching and learning. Conversely, music software and educational applications recorded the lowest among the extensive ratings ($M = 3.38$), suggesting a relatively moderate integration of digital tools for composition, theory, and collaboration. Nonetheless, all domains received ratings consistent with extensive availability, reflecting a well-rounded approach to resource allocation in music programs.

and performance skills improve significantly when they are provided with access to varied musical environments, such as well-equipped rehearsal spaces and a broad range of instruments. Furthermore, Southcott and Joseph (2021) advocate for the expansion of music libraries and digital repositories to ensure that all learners, regardless of context, have equitable access to resources. Overall, the findings confirm that the schools involved in the study are well-resourced,

Table 1. Extent of Availability of Musical Resources in Schools

No	Extent of Availability of Musical Resources in Schools	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Quantity and variety of instruments	3.40	Extensive
2	Technology and audiovisual equipment	3.74	Extensive
3	Music software and educational applications	3.38	Extensive
4	Music libraries and sheet music	3.42	Extensive
5	Rehearsal spaces	3.48	Extensive
Mean Average		3.49	Extensive

providing a conducive learning environment that supports the holistic development of musical skills and fosters student engagement.

3.2. *Extent of Music Education Outcomes*—Music education outcomes refer to the measurable results and holistic developments that learners achieve through structured and intentional participation in music instruction. These outcomes encompass a range of cognitive, affective, psychomotor, and social dimensions that reflect both the academic and expressive goals of music education. In this study, music education outcomes are operationalized through four indicators: student musical proficiency, performance quality, creativity and expression, and ensemble participation. At the core of music education is musical proficiency, which includes students’ technical skills, sight-reading ability, auditory discrimination, and theoretical knowledge. These proficiencies serve as foundational competencies, enabling learners to engage meaningfully with diverse musical forms and practices. According to Hash (2021), the systematic development of musical proficiency is a key marker of effective music instruction and correlates strongly with sustained student engagement and achievement. Performance quality, on the other hand, refers to the expressive and technical excellence demonstrated during individual or group presentations. This in-

cludes intonation, rhythm accuracy, stage presence, and overall musical interpretation. As articulated by Major and Rupley (2022), consistent access to quality instruction and rehearsal environments significantly enhances students’ performance outcomes and nurtures their confidence in public presentations. Beyond technical skills, creativity and expression capture the personal and interpretive dimensions of music learning. This includes improvisation, composition, and the ability to convey emotions through musical interpretation. Barrett (2023) emphasizes that creativity is not only a desirable outcome but also a core component of music education, fostering critical thinking and emotional intelligence. Lastly, ensemble participation reflects the social and collaborative aspects of music learning. It involves teamwork, practical listening skills, leadership, and a shared sense of musical purpose. Participation in ensembles promotes discipline, cooperation, and a sense of belonging among learners, as supported by Hoffman and Carter (2021), who argue that ensemble-based activities cultivate not only musical competence but also interpersonal development. Collectively, music education outcomes serve as vital indicators of the success and impact of music programs in schools. They provide educators with a multidimensional framework for assessing student growth and for

designing inclusive, responsive, and culturally rich curricula. Table 2 summarizes the extent of music education outcomes in the participating schools across four major domains: student musical proficiency, performance quality, creativity and expression, and ensemble participation. The computed overall mean score is 2.84, inter-

preted as Moderately Extensive. This suggests that while schools provide structured music programs that address multiple dimensions of student development, there remains considerable room for enhancement in fostering deeper and more consistent musical outcomes.

Table 2. Extent of Music Education Outcomes

No	Extent of Music Education Outcomes	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Student musical proficiency	2.76	Moderately Extensive
2	Performance quality	2.76	Moderately Extensive
3	Creativity and expression	2.61	Moderately Extensive
4	Ensemble participation	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Mean Average		2.84	Moderately Extensive

Among the four indicators, ensemble participation registered the highest mean score (M = 3.22), indicating that collaborative music-making is the most consistently implemented and emphasized domain across schools. This affirms the value placed on teamwork, group rehearsals, and community-building aspects of music education. On the other hand, creativity and expression received the lowest rating (M = 2.61), suggesting that opportunities for original composition, improvisation, and expressive interpretation may be limited in current instructional practices. Both student musical proficiency and performance quality recorded mean scores of 2.76, also interpreted as Moderately Extensive. These results indicate moderate levels of technical skill development and public performance exposure. However, they also highlight gaps in the consistency of instruction, access to individualized support, and professional-level evaluation mechanisms. These findings are supported by current literature. According to Hash (2021), ensemble participation strengthens student engagement and musical sensitivity, particularly when supported by structured re-

hearsal frameworks. However, as noted by Barrett (2023), many music programs underrepresent creativity and composition, often focusing more on replicating performance than fostering student innovation. Likewise, Major and Rupley (2022) emphasize that consistent feedback, adjudication, and exposure to authentic performance experiences are crucial for raising performance quality and musical confidence—areas that appear to be only moderately addressed in the present context. In summary, while the schools demonstrate a commendable level of engagement in various aspects of music education, the results indicate a need for more intensive integration of creativity, individualized proficiency-building, and performance excellence strategies to optimize student musical outcomes.

3.3. *Relationship Between the Availability of Musical Resources in School and Music Education Outcomes*—Table 3 presents the result of the Pearson correlation analysis conducted to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the availability of musical resources in school and the music education outcomes among students in the participating

schools. The analysis yielded a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.065$ with a corresponding p-value of 0.477. Given that the p-value exceeds the standard significance level of 0.05, the relation-

ship is interpreted as not statistically significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H) stating that there is no significant relationship between the two variables is accepted.

Table 3. Relationship between Availability of Musical Resources in School and Music Education Outcomes

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Availability of Musical Resources in School	0.065	0.477	Not Significant	Accept H_0

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

This finding suggests that while musical resources, such as instruments, technology, rehearsal spaces, software, and sheet music, are generally available to a considerable extent, their presence does not automatically translate into improved music education outcomes unless coupled with effective pedagogical practices, student engagement strategies, and high-quality instruction. This underscores the notion that resource availability is a necessary but not sufficient condition for enhancing music learning results. Comparable findings have been reported in prior research. For instance, Abril and Bannerman (2022) emphasized that the mere provision of musical materials and technology does not guarantee learning gains unless these resources are meaningfully integrated into instruction through teacher training and student-centered methodologies. Similarly, Hash and Lindeman (2021) highlighted that the impact of school resources on student achievement is mediated by factors such as teacher competence, curriculum design, and school leadership support. In this light, the results of the present study affirm the growing consensus that the quality of music education outcomes depends not solely on access to tools, but on how those tools are used within the educational process. Thus, while it remains essential for schools to maintain and improve their musical infras-

structure, greater attention should be given to capacity-building, instructional innovation, and assessment-driven teaching to ensure that available resources yield meaningful learning results.

3.4. Domains of Availability of Musical Resources in School Significantly Influence Music Education Outcomes—The Model Summary table presents the goodness-of-fit indicators for the regression model predicting music education outcomes (MEO_AVE) based on five domains of musical resource availability: quantity and variety of instruments (A_AVE), technology and audiovisual equipment (B_AVE), music software and educational applications (C_AVE), music libraries and sheet music (D_AVE), and rehearsal spaces (E_AVE). The other predictors, Quantity and Variety of Instruments (QVI), Technology and Audiovisual Equipment (TAE), Music Software and Educational Applications (MSEA), and Music Libraries and Sheet Music (MLSM), did not show significant effects, with p-values greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for those variables. These findings are supported by Jellison and Draper (2022), who emphasized that acoustically optimized and technologically integrated rehearsal spaces substantially enhance music performance outcomes and ensemble cohesiveness. Furthermore, Veblen and Mantie (2021) observed that the flexibility and functionality of

rehearsal environments are key enablers of both individual and collaborative musical growth. These findings are supported by Jellison and Draper (2022), who emphasized that acoustically optimized and technologically integrated rehearsal spaces substantially enhance music performance outcomes and ensemble cohesiveness. Furthermore, Veblen and Mantie (2021) observed that the flexibility and functionality of rehearsal environments are key enablers of both individual and collaborative musical growth.

Table 4. Adaptation Strategies that Significantly Influence Learning Outcomes

Model	Variable	Unstandardized B	Standard Error	Standardized Beta	t	p-value	Decision
M ₀	(Intercept)	2.842	0.070	—	40.669	< .001	—
M ₁	(Intercept)	2.978	0.489	—	6.085	< .001	—
	QVI	0.115	0.149	0.162	0.772	0.442	Accept Null
	TAE	-0.324	0.240	-0.286	-1.351	0.179	Accept Null
	MSEA	-0.311	0.192	-0.442	-1.621	0.108	Accept Null
	MLSM	0.169	0.151	0.245	1.115	0.267	Accept Null
	RS	0.333	0.123	0.439	2.715	0.008	Reject Null

Note: Significant at p < 0.05

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions drawn from the study’s findings on the availability of musical resources and their impact on music education outcomes in selected schools within the Mati Northwest District, Mati North West District, and Mati City Schools Division. The conclusions are anchored on the results of both descriptive and inferential analyses. At the same time, the recommendations are proposed to guide school leaders, music educators, and stakeholders in enhancing the delivery and effectiveness of music education programs.

4.1. Findings—On the extent of availability of musical resources in schools. The study revealed that the overall extent of musical resource availability in schools was rated as extensive. Among the identified domains, technology and audiovisual equipment emerged as the most extensively available, followed by rehearsal spaces, music libraries, sheet music, the quantity and variety of instruments, and music software and educational applications. These findings indicate that schools are generally well-equipped with modern infrastructure and tools. However, software-based and individualized resources remain areas that may benefit from further enhancement. On the extent of music education outcomes among students. The outcomes of music education were generally perceived as moderately extensive. Collaborative engagement through ensemble participation was the most evident, while domains such as student musical proficiency, performance quality, creativity, and expression were perceived to a lesser extent. This suggests that schools emphasize group performance and technical execution, whereas instructional support for creativity, composition, and improvisation warrants greater attention. On the relationship between the availability of musical resources and music

education outcomes. The results of the correlation analysis indicated no statistically significant relationship between the availability of musical resources and students' music education outcomes. This suggests that while material resources are present in schools, their mere availability does not necessarily translate to improved educational results unless paired with effective pedagogical strategies and active teacher facilitation. On the specific domains of musical resources that significantly influence music education outcomes. Findings from the regression analysis identified rehearsal spaces as the only domain with a statistically significant influence on music education outcomes. Other domains, including the quantity and variety of instruments, technology and audiovisual equipment, music software and applications, and music libraries, did not show notable effects. This underscores the importance of functional and dedicated rehearsal environments in enhancing musical development, ensemble performance quality, and student engagement.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: **Availability of Musical Resources.** Schools in the Mati Northwest District, Mati North West District, and Mati City Schools Division demonstrate an extensive availability of musical resources, particularly in technology and audiovisual equipment. However, the moderately extensive availability of music software and individualized tools suggests a need for a more balanced distribution of traditional and digital instructional materials. **Extent of Music Education Outcomes.** Music education outcomes are rated as moderately extensive, with the highest strengths in ensemble participation and relatively lower outcomes in creativity and expression. This indicates a functional but not fully optimized music learning experience, where students are more engaged in performance routines than in creative or individualized musical development. **Relationship Between Resources and**

Outcomes. There is no statistically significant relationship between the overall availability of musical resources and the level of music education outcomes. **Significant Predictor of Learning Outcomes.** Among all resource domains, only rehearsal spaces significantly predict music education outcomes. This highlights the importance of creating conducive, accessible, and acoustically supportive rehearsal environments to achieve high-quality musical performances and skill development.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed: **To the Learners.** Learners are encouraged to actively engage with all available musical resources, including digital tools and educational applications, as part of their learning process. They should explore opportunities for independent practice in composition, improvisation, and expressive performance, thereby enhancing their creativity and broadening their musical experience beyond ensemble activities. **To the Teachers.** Teachers are encouraged to refine their instructional strategies by maximizing the integration of existing musical resources into their teaching practices. Participation in professional development programs that emphasize student-centered approaches, particularly those focusing on composition, improvisation, and creative expression, is recommended. Teachers should also foster an inclusive learning environment that nurtures both technical proficiency and artistic individuality. **To the School Heads.** School heads are advised to prioritize the development and enhancement of dedicated rehearsal spaces, recognizing their significant contribution to music education outcomes. Investments in acoustically treated, well-equipped, and adaptable rehearsal facilities will enable more effective ensemble instruction and student engagement. Furthermore, school leaders should support faculty initiatives that align with the school's overall vision for music education. **To the Department of Edu-**

cation (DepEd) Officials. DepEd officials are encouraged to establish clear guidelines that link musical resource planning to pedagogical and curricular goals. Budget allocations and procurement of musical tools and equipment should be informed by instructional needs rather than availability alone. Moreover, policies that support the continued training of music teachers, as well as the improvement of physical learning environments, should be institutionalized. To the Future Researchers. Future researchers are encouraged to investigate other variables that may impact music education outcomes, such as teacher competencies, student motivation, or community involvement. Longitudinal or mixed-methods studies examining the long-term impact of musical resource utilization and instructional innovations would further enrich the understanding of effective practices in music education.

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